

An informed peer review framework for thrust-area performance-based funding

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Abstract

Research assessment for funding decisions, especially at individual level for thrust-areas is one of the major challenges that are being faced by nations. Owing to the limitations of peer review process as well as the quantitative/scientometric indicators for this purpose, informed peer review is widely explored as a reliable option. However, the limitations of existing widely used indicators such as h-index and impact factor and lack of systematic procedure to ensure coordination of both the approaches for a decision framework is posing challenges to informed peer review. In this work, two indicators namely relevance-incorporated expertise indices are devised and a framework that consists of quantitative/scientometric assessment framework and decision framework is developed. The framework, especially the quantitative framework, is illustrated and it is found that the relevance-incorporated expertise indices are more advantageous and useful than h and g indices and this ensures the usability of the framework for informed peer review process.

Introduction

National level policymakers are forced to form special organizations or special funding programs for fostering research within some areas (especially new or emerging areas) that are globally viewed as promising ones. These fields are often dubbed as national priority areas or thrust areas. For instance, back in 2006, an Indian working group on thrust areas hand-picked cyber security, multi-scale modelling, Quantum theory and applications, etc., as some of the thrust areas in engineering sciences. The establishment of the Interdisciplinary Cyber Physical Systems (ICPS) division by the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Govt. of India is another evidence of the increasing emphasis on ‘thrust area performance-based’ funding. One of the key challenges faced by research evaluators especially for funding of research project proposal or award of fellowships in thrust-areas of research is the responsible use of indicators, especially when the thrust-area is in an emerging phase. Evaluation and decision-making that is purely based on peer-review can be tricky because of the availability of a few experts to form panels or committees, in which case the funding agencies often invite pioneers in related fields as best bet. Major risk in this is the chances of inherent judgemental bias in varied level owing to the dominance of one or few proactive members that in turn depends on the qualitative parameters/criteria used for sound judgements in their own areas of expertise. The rising reputation of Scientometric/bibliometric indicators for quantitative assessment despite some caveats led to the inclusion of these indicators either as an initial screening-mechanism or as a decisive tool in all the phases of the review process depending on the awareness and confidence of the decision-makers about the best use of indicators to complement peer review as in ‘informed peer review’. However, the lack of proper understanding (due to lack of training in Scientometrics) of the evaluators about the purpose of design, conditions for usage, strength and weakness of available indicators might have led either to the usage of wrong indicators or

misuse of indicators. The misuse of the legendary ‘Impact Factor’ metric (Garfield, 1963), that later forced the introduction of Field Normalized Impact Factor (Dorta-Gonzalez & Dorta-Gonzalez, 2013; Leydesdorff et al., 2013) and Source Normalized Impact Factor (Leydesdorff & Opthof, 2010), is one of the greatest examples in this regard. Another unhealthy practice is the reliance on not-so-properly designed (by one or more committee members who are not so well-trained in Scientometrics) ad hoc evaluation procedures using some indicator. The reuse of these erstwhile poorly-designed procedures for future evaluations, especially in different time and for different subject can be of even more gravity.

Another indicator that was a crucial landmark in Scientometric literature is the h -index by Hirsch (2005). Though the conditions for which it can be best used and not used was mentioned by Hirsch himself and many others who come up with indicators that formed a genre known as h -type indicators, the misuse of the h -index still continues in various assessments including informed peer review owing mostly to the ease and convenience it offers to the evaluators. Some of the h -type indicators that offer more stability than the h -index and reflect ‘offsetability’ or the effect of citations at the top-order in a better way are g -index (Egghe, 2006) and Ψ -index (Lathabai, 2020). Apart from the concern of accommodation of offsetability, another drawback of the h -index is the advantage enjoyed by experienced scholars or the ones who had a long span of career. Though this limitation is inherited by both g and Ψ , the offsetability counteracts or dilutes this effect to some extent in the case of younger scholars (young in terms of active research period) if their works are moderately or well-cited. This being the case at the individual level, the usage of h -index for institutional performance assessment can be detrimental. This is discussed next.

The usage of h -index for institutional performance assessment is heavily advantageous to old and well-established institutions than relatively newer ones in a much higher scale than that in the case of individuals possibly because of the following reasons. The old institutions might be having more papers (that might have earned far better citations than the newer ones) from many research areas published by a very long list of historical as well as current scholars. However, the newer institution might be having more competency in one or few areas than the other one. But h -index is not capable of capturing such competency as it is designed to be an overall productivity indicator. Recently, Lathabai et al. (2021) developed a framework for institutional productivity assessment based on expertise/competencies of institutions in a field which in turn is determined using strength of that institution in different thematic areas within that field. Major expertise indices used in the framework are x -index and $x(g)$ -index, which are inspired from h -index and g -index. However, unlike h -index that reflects the number of h publications having h or more citations, x -index indicates the number of x thematic areas (in which that institution published) having thematic strength of at least x , where thematic strength is determined by suitable measures such as number of citations earned by the institution in that thematic area. Similarly, $x(g)$ -index gives the number of $x(g)$ thematic areas such that the average thematic strength remains at least $x(g)$. Like h and g indices partition the citation profile of an individual into h -core, h -tail and g -core, g -tail respectively, the x and $x(g)$ indices partition the research strength profile of an institution into x -core, x -tail and $x(g)$ -core, $x(g)$ -tail respectively. The top x themes that belong to x -core are the core competency areas and the subsequent ones that occupy next $(x(g)-x)$ positions (i.e., positions from $x+1$ to $x(g)$) are the potential core competency areas of the institution. This is an added advantage that is helpful for research portfolio management that involve planning for expansion of core competencies by strengthening the potential core competency areas.

At individual level too, core competencies and potential core competencies exist. Insights about core competencies and potential core competencies can be useful for individual level

performance assessment too. Especially when thrust-area performance is assessed, it will be very advantageous if the applicant is having expertise in the intended thrust-area or closely related thematic areas (details of the same is given in Methodology section). As in the case of institutions, *h*-index and *h*-type indicators cannot reflect the expertise of individuals too. Can the recently introduced expertise indices (originally introduced for assessment of institutions) be adapted to be used at the individual level? If so, can this be incorporated into a framework of informed peer review? These are the research questions that we pursue in this work. Therefore, we attempt to explore the possibilities of usage of expertise indices for the individual scholars. This is followed by the development of a decision framework based on thematic strengths and expertise indices of scholars to quantitatively evaluate the scholar profiles for informed peer review of project proposals/fellowship applications in thrust areas. Also, funding agencies who hold historical data of the profiles of those who were funded may use this framework to rank the scholars at a point of time and track the progress of their portfolio by reusing the framework at another point of time (possibly after the award of a grant/fellowship). Another novelty of this work lies in the fact that, unlike the expertise indices by Lathabai et al. (2021), the proposed framework uses the relevance score of the concept/keyword associated with publications at the affiliation network creation phase to create the relevance weighted paper-keyword/concept affiliation networks and as a result the relevance-incorporated expertise indices obtained can be represented as $x^{[R]}$ and $x(g)^{[R]}$. This is discussed in the section on ‘Methodology’. Before that, a brief discussion of major existing performance-based funding systems and indicators used for standalone quantitative analysis or for supporting informed-peer review is discussed.

Related research on methods and indicators used in performance-based research funding systems

In the past three decades, the performance-based funding regime is found to be replacing trust-based funding regime with an objective to promote vertical differentiation and functional specialization between institutions while at the same time secure horizontal diversity and pluralism within the system (Sorlin, 2007). In case of performance-based research funding systems (PRFSs), the Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) that was launched in 1986 is one of the first of its kind (Hicks, 2012) which has moved towards REF (Research Excellence Framework). After that, owing to the timely shift in national research policies, many countries introduced PRFS. Major PRFSs of Spain (Marini, 2018), Slovak Republic (Geuna & Martin, 2003), Hong Kong (French et al., 2001), Australia (Marginson, 1997), Poland (Kulczycki et al., 2017), Portugal (Deem, 2016), Italy (Mateos-González & Boliver, 2019), New Zealand, (Hodder & Hodder, 2010), Belgium (Debackere & Glänzel, 2004), Norway (Sivertsen, 2009), Sweden (Hammarfelt et al., 2016), Denmark (Deutz et al., 2021), Finland (Mathies et al., 2020), etc., are some of the flourishing systems, that have undergone periodic evaluation and revision. Major dimensions in which these systems vary are in their unit of analysis, methods of measurement, frequency and census period. Costs of implementing of PRFS (that includes both direct and indirect costs) is a major concern for governments. For instance, RAE (UK) and VTR (Italy) incurred heavy costs due to expensive peer-review exercises for faculty assessment (Harman, 2000). Possible units of evaluation of performance for funding/resource allocation decision can be individuals, research groups, departments and universities. Evaluation for PRFS is challenging and the level and nature of challenges vary at different levels of analysis. Even more challenging than the evaluation of study of the effect of PRFS system for decision is its periodic revision/amendment.

Among the above-mentioned systems, analysis at the level of departments and field-in-Universities are mostly found. There are a few that conduct assessment at the level of

universities (institutional level) and individual level. For instance, ‘sexino’ system of Spain and ‘PBRF’ system of New Zealand assesses individual performance. While the former is used to determine salary increments, the latter is aggregated into a rating for universities to decide on block funding allocations. Old Australian system that was adopted by the Norwegian (Aagaard et al., 2015) and Danish systems (Deutz et al., 2021) also are institutional level assessment systems. When it comes to methods used for assessment, mostly peer review is found to be used for departmental and field evaluations in Italian and Portuguese systems. The ERA system of Australia permits choice of peer review or metrics for field evaluation. University-level evaluations are mostly dependent on quantitative formulas that uses bibliometric outputs. Among these bibliometric indicators, publication counts, journal impact factor (by Clarivate Analytics), citation information, etc., are used.

When it comes to assessment at individual level, most of the assessment committees go for peer review. This is also the case among countries where well-defined PRFS is in place, for instance among the above-discussed countries, Spain and New Zealand uses peer review at individual level. There were studies that investigated the effectiveness of peer review (i) in contrast to the performance indicated by indices like *h*-index (Bornmann, et al., 2008) and (ii) with respect to different factors that can induce bias in peer review process other than the judgemental bias in quality assessment like done by Tamblyn et al., (2018). However, Joint Committee on Quantitative Assessment of Research formed by three major international Mathematics institutions dismissed the usage of *h*-index for individual and institutional performance assessment as they shown it as naive (Adler et al., 2009). Among the countries or organizations that uses purely indicator-based research assessment or indicator-based as well as peer review combination for research assessment that are widely known as informed peer review, misuse of indicators, especially the ones like Impact Factor (IF) and *h*-index, cautioned by Garfield (1963; 2004) are found. For instance, Indian funding agencies are being criticized for not only the wrong use of IF and *h*-index, but also for institutionalization of such misuse (Madhan et al., 2018). When it comes to Journal IF, the declaration during the Annual Meeting of the American Society for Cell Biology in San Francisco in 2012, dubbed as Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), is garnering attention and endorsement from academic communities around the globe, clearly recommended against the usage of JIF for individual research articles, to assess an individual scientist’s contributions, or in hiring, promotion, or funding decisions (Moher et al., 2018). All these again strengthens the usability of informed peer review despite its limitations. The need for checking the feasibility of effective combination of bibliometric and peer review process for effective research assessment was emphasized by Butler (2007) & Moed (2007). One attempt for such an evaluation can be attributed to Bertocchi et al. (2015) through the investigation of correlation between bibliometric and peer review evaluations in the context of Italian VQR system. Considering the cost and time required for quantitative assessment based on bibliometrics and informed peer review, Abramo & D’Angelo (2011) opined quantitative/bibliometric approach as far preferable over informed peer review in natural and formal sciences. Amid these ongoing debates, the importance of peer review and informed peer review, even in disciplines that are having life-saving potential is still being advocated as done by Kharasch et al. (2021).

Thus, unless there is an indicator or set of indicators and a systematic procedure with which these indicators can be used for a flawless research assessment at individual level or at any level for that matter, the usage of informed peer review after rectifying its limitations (other than the time and cost, that roots from limitations of indicators and their application context) seems to be the best choice. However, the existence of IF and *h*-index syndrome (Madhan et al., 2018) in many organized and not-so-organized PRFS systems, demands the need for a better indicator

and a framework that can be used for informed peer review as we mentioned in the introduction. This gap is attempted to be addressed in this work.

Methodology

Informed peer review can be best done with two teams of experts- one for quantitative/Scientometric analysis and other for qualitative analysis/peer review, where the first team should work independently of the second one. Once the analysis of the performance of applicants are done by the first team and results are ready, this team shall pass the results to the second team responsible for conducting peer review of the proposals for grants/applications for fellowships. Funding agencies, especially the ones run by Government should consider hiring experts for quantitative/Scientometric analysis and build and maintain a good team for that or properly train existing competitive employees in Scientometric analysis to build a good team. The evaluation report of the first team can be forwarded to the second team to be used for a kind of initial screening for elimination of some applicants' proposals if their expertise does not match well with the thematic area(s) for which funding is to be allotted, especially if the proposal does not seem to be that impressive in the first glance itself. Possible decision situations encountered prior to the qualitative assessment of merit of submissions by the second team is attempted to be highlighted and based on that a decision framework is also proposed. Before that, the quantitative/scientometric assessment framework, that can be useful to the first team is discussed.

Quantitative/Scientometric framework

As already discussed, a promising way to inform the second committee about the expertise areas of each applicant and the strength of applicants in such areas is by the usage of framework for determination of expertise indices (Lathabai et al., 2021). These expertise indices can determine the core competency and potential core competency areas of the research of an individual/ institution. However, that framework treats each author-given keywords as equally relevant to that publication. This might cause some kind of biases or inflations. To avoid that a mechanism to know the relevance score is required. As the 'Dimensions' database (<https://app.dimensions.ai/>) provides the relevance scores of each 'concepts' that are extracted from a publication, the scores associated with concept can be assigned to 'author keywords' through a matching process. In this way, we will get a relevance weighted Paper-Keyword network unlike the Paper-Keyword network obtained by Lathabai et al. (2021).

From this point onwards, most of the procedures are same as that given by Lathabai et al. (2021). Thus, the step-by-step procedure of the computation of relevance-incorporated expertise indices $x^{[R]}$ and $x(g)^{[R]}$ is given below and depicted in fig. 1.

Step 1. From the biodata or CV submitted by the author prepare the list of publications or if the list of publications provided by the author, determine the author-provided keywords against each publication by searching a suitable database like WoS. In a WoS file, the field tag 'DE' represents author keywords. Now, using this a Paper-Keyword affiliation network, (W-K) can be created as done by Lathabai et al. (2021). However, as we are interested to have the effect of relevance of keywords too, we need to extract the concept scores and create relevance weighted Paper-Keyword network. This is the second and most crucial step that contributes to the novelty of this work.

Step 2. From 'Dimensions' database, for each publication, extract the concepts associated with each publication along with the relevance scores. This extraction can be controlled by applying a relevance score threshold (say ≥ 0.1 or so if the profile of the author does not contain too many papers or papers are found to have too many concepts, otherwise some greater score of

relevance score like 0.5 or 0.6 can be set as threshold). Now, in a similar fashion as done in the first step, create a Paper-Concept affiliation network but with relevance scores as weights, denoted by $W-C^{[R]}$. Now, through the following procedure, the unweighted $W-K$ network and relevance-weighted $W-C$ network can be used to create relevance-weighted $W-K$ network.

- A) $\forall w_i = w_j, w_i \in W$ of $W-K$ network and $w_j \in W$ of $W-C^{[R]}$ network, if $k_m = c_n, k_m \in K$ in $W-K$ network and $c_n \in C$ in $W-C^{[R]}$ network,
Then update $p_{w_i k_m}$, the weight of arc from w_i to k_m in $W-K$ network as

$$p_{w_i k_m} : p_{w_i k_m} \times p_{w_j c_n}$$

Since default value of $p_{w_i k_m}$ is 1, the new weight of the arc from w_i to k_m will be equal to $p_{w_j c_n}$. This can be regarded as an injection as defined by Lathabai et al. (2017).

Fig. 1 Scientometric/quantitative framework showing double Injection methodology for relevance-incorporated thematic strength and expertise computation

Upon the completion of the above step, unweighted $W-K$ network will become relevance weighted $W-K$ network or $W-K^{[R]}$. In case if there are too many keywords in $W-K^{[R]}$, NLP module can be used as done by Lathabai et al. (2021) to process the concept list. Otherwise, it can be optional. Now, suitable attribute score that can represent thematic strength (like citations earned by publications) have to be injected into the relevance-weighted $W-K$ network. This is the next step.

Step 3. In this step, $\forall w_i \in W$ in $W-K^{[R]}$, if e_i is the citation earned by w_i (from Dimensions), update weight of every arc from w_i to K as

$$p_{w_i k_m} : p_{w_i k_m} \times e_i$$

Upon completion of the above injection process, we will get citation weighted $W-K^{[R]}$ network that can be denoted by $W-K^{[R]*}$. As, this methodology uses two injection processes (one in step 2 and other in step 3), it can be regarded as double injection methodology.

Next step is the computation of thematic strengths (relevance-incorporated) from the $W-K^{[R]*}$ network.

Step 4. In a weighted directed network, weighted indegree of a vertex indicates the sum of weights of incoming arcs to that vertex. For citation weighted relevance-incorporated W-K network obtained in step 3, the weighted indegree of keyword gives the strength of publications by the author in that thematic area (represented by the keyword) with the implicit effect of relevance which can be termed as the relevance-incorporated thematic strength. Now for every author, we can have thematic profile having relevance-incorporated strengths of each thematic area. Now relevance incorporated expertise indices $x^{[R]}$ and $x(g)^{[R]}$ can be computed in same fashion as that of x and $x(g)$ computation by Lathabai et al., (2021). These indices are defined as:

$x^{[R]}$ -index: A Scientist is supposed to have an $x^{[R]}$ -index value of $x^{[R]}$ if he has published papers in at least $x^{[R]}$ thematic areas with relevance-incorporated thematic strengths exceeding $x^{[R]}$. These $x^{[R]}$ areas that form the $x^{[R]}$ -core can be treated as the core competency areas of the Scientist.

$x(g)^{[R]}$ -index: A Scientist is supposed to have an $x(g)^{[R]}$ -index value of $x(g)^{[R]}$ if he has published papers in at least $x(g)^{[R]}$ thematic areas such that the average relevance-incorporated thematic strength from these areas exceeds $x(g)^{[R]}$.

Most important thing about the $x(g)^{[R]}$ core is that, apart from the top $x^{[R]}$ areas it holds next ($x(g)^{[R]}$ - $x^{[R]}$ areas), that can be treated as potential core competency areas. The term ‘potential core competency area’ is used because these areas can become core competency of the Scientist in immediate future.

Determination of $x^{[R]}$ -core and $x(g)^{[R]}$ -core from weighted indegree results

From the sorted profile of an author (sorted by weighted indegrees of keywords), $x^{[R]}$ -index of an author can be computed.

$x^{[R]}$ -index satisfies the following condition.

$$x^{[R]} = \{ \max_i : \text{weighted indegree of keyword at position } i > i \}$$

$x(g)^{[R]}$ -index satisfies the following condition.

$$x(g)^{[R]} = \{ \max_i : \sum_i \text{weighted indegree of keyword at position } i > i^2 \}$$

where, i is an arbitrary rank/position of sorted keywords (sorted by weighted indegrees).

Thus, at the end of the exercise done using quantitative/Scientometric framework, the first team can give the profiles of individual applicants with the following information: different thematic areas associated with the applicant and the strengths of the applicants in each thematic area (relevance-incorporated strength), core competency areas of the applicants, potential core competency areas of the applicants.

Decision framework for shortlisting

As discussed in the introduction, most challenging task for reviewers for evaluation of project proposal or grant application, especially for thrust area funding, can be determination of the level/degree of match between the expertise of the applicant and the themes for which grant/fellowship is to be provided. This normally requires the reading of all or at least some of the publications that seems to be related to the areas (from their title or abstract), going through the themes of focus/scope of the journals or the outlets through which these papers are published, etc. Most of the expert reviewers neither have time to do all these nor does not care to do so. Sometimes, administrative staff with only basic educational qualifications might be

entrusted with this task. As they might be instructed to check the quality of outlet/sources in which these publications came, mostly by using Impact Factor (IF), most of the applicants having publishing history in one or few good publications in journals having IF will be forwarded to peer review unless it is obvious that the themes handled by the journals are too distant or dissimilar from the theme of the grant/fellowship.

This problem is supposed to be addressed to some extent by the above quantitative framework. Once the information about different thematic areas associated with the applicant and the strengths of the applicants in each thematic area (relevance-incorporated strength), core competency areas of the applicants, potential core competency areas of the applicants are obtained, the following questions can be answered:

1. How many of the themes associated with the grant/fellowship can be found in the core competency area of the applicant?
2. How many of the themes associated with the grant/fellowship can be found in the potential core competency area of the applicant?
3. How much is the strength of the applicant in each thematic area associated with the fellowship if it is found in core competency or potential core competency area of the applicant?

Suppose if T represents the set of thematic areas considered for the fellowship and let t be the total number of thematic areas in T . Let $T_{x^{[R]}}$ and $T_{x(g)^{[R]}}$ be the set of thematic areas present in the $x^{[R]}$ -core and $x(g)^{[R]}$ -core of the applicant, with $x^{[R]}$ and $x(g)^{[R]}$ being the total number of themes areas in $T_{x^{[R]}}$ and $T_{x(g)^{[R]}}$ respectively, then set of themes related to the grant/fellowship programme that falls within core competency of the applicant can be found out as $T \cap T_{x^{[R]}}$. So, the level of agreement of the core expertise of applicant and thematic orientation of the programme can be computed as:

$$\alpha = \frac{|T \cap T_{x^{[R]}}|}{|T|} = \frac{|T \cap T_{x^{[R]}}|}{t} \quad (1)$$

And the level of agreement of the potential core expertise of applicant and thematic orientation of the programme can be computed as:

$$\beta = \frac{|T \cap (T_{x(g)^{[R]}}/T_{x^{[R]}})|}{|T|} = \frac{|T \cap (T_{x(g)^{[R]}}/T_{x^{[R]}})|}{t} \quad (2)$$

Closer the value of α to 1, higher the level of agreement between core competency of the applicant and thematic orientation of the programme. Similarly, closer the value of β to 1, higher the level of agreement between potential core competency of the applicant and thematic orientation of the programme.

Now, for each applicant, for each thematic area listed in $T \cap T_{x^{[R]}}$, note down the thematic strengths. Suppose $|T \cap T_{x^{[R]}}|=n$ and S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n be the strengths of the applicant associated with the thematic areas in the set T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n in the set $T \cap T_{x^{[R]}}$, then the normalized strength of the applicant in these areas can be computed as:

$$\gamma = \frac{S_1+S_2+\dots+S_n}{\max.S_1+\max.S_2+\dots+\max.S_n} \quad (3)$$

Where, $\max.S_1, \max.S_2, \dots, \max.S_n$, etc., are the highest possible strengths by all the applicants in the list related to the themes represented by T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n in the case of first applicant.

Closer the value of γ to 1, higher the possibility of the applicant being most strong in all the thematic areas related to the funding programme.

Similarly, for each applicant, for each thematic area listed in $T \cap T \cap (T_x(g)^{[R]}/T_x^{[R]})$, note down the thematic strengths. Suppose $|T \cap (T_x(g)^{[R]}/T_x^{[R]})|=m$ and R_1, R_2, \dots, R_m be the strengths of the applicant associated with the thematic areas in the set T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m in the set $T \cap (T_x(g)^{[R]}/T_x^{[R]})$, then the normalized strength of the applicant in these areas can be computed as:

$$\delta = \frac{R_1 + R_2 + \dots + R_m}{\max.R_1 + \max.R_2 + \dots + \max.R_m} \quad (4)$$

Where, $\max.R_1, \max.R_2, \dots, \max.R_m$, etc., are the highest possible strengths by all the applicants in the list related to the themes represented by T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m in the case of first applicant.

Now, to reduce the possible effect of small number of publications in thematic area with high citations on the thematic strengths and consequently γ , a composite score (CS), which is weighted composite of α, β, γ and δ can be used in the following way:

$$CS = 0.35 \alpha + 0.15 \beta + 0.35 \gamma + 0.15 \delta \quad (5)$$

Now, before ranking the applicants based on CS value, the applicants should be grouped together according to their effective age/span of activity in the ‘thrust area’. This will help to avoid the problems with comparing differently experienced applicants. The procedure of informed peer review framework proposed in this work up to this stage is shown in fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Informed peer review framework up to peer review procedure where the scientometric framework is depicted in fig. 1.

Then within each group, proposals submitted by low scoring applicants (based on a suitable threshold/ cut-off) can be handled first by the expert committee to perform qualitative peer review based on qualitative parameters. Proposals that can be found promising despite its low score can be reserved for the shortlisting (as per the two possible scenarios that are discussed shortly) while other proposals shall be turned down. Then, the high scoring proposals can be reviewed qualitatively, and promising ones can be considered for shortlisting depending on the number of grant/fellowships that can be awarded.

For instance, if the total number of awards is N , and the number of effective age-based groups is M , shortlist ($y N/M$) (where y can be 2, 3, etc., depending on the value of N and the time funding agency can spent on the selection process), rationality can be rounded off properly. Otherwise, out of M groups, if proposals from certain groups are not entertained (say too much experienced or too early stage), consider only M^* groups where $M^*=M$ - number of groups not considered. Then shortlisting can be done for ($y N/M^*$) applicants in each group.

As we already mentioned, since peer review process use several qualitative factors- both generic aspects of the proposal and subject specific aspects of the proposal, we are not discussing the peer review part in detail as the funding agency or those who administrate the selection process is supposed to ensure standard peer review process that prevails for the concerned discipline. However, as a study by Van den Besselaar (2017) found that an equally large group of non-selected applicants performed at least as well as the selected applicants, it was concluded that selecting the best in peer review process is too strong a claim. Similar conclusions were made by Hornbostel et al. (2009) and Bornmann et al. (2010), shedding new light to the earlier conclusions by Van den Besselaar & Leydesdorff (2009) and Leeuwen & Moed (2012) that on average, successful applications perform better than non-selected applicants. The new conclusion reinforces the speculation that proposals that support the main stream have higher possibility of being awarded than the ones that deviates from main stream or showcases novelty beyond a level. Therefore, one recommendation we make about the qualitative peer review part of the framework is that 'novelty' should be a prime quality that is evaluated (subjected to the feasibility and availability of funds). But it is not prudent to provide a 'rule of thumb' in this regard because how novelty can be assessed and to what extent novelty can be encouraged poses challenge. It can be done only on 'case by case' basis in a specific discipline. However, as thrust-areas or national priority areas are research areas a nation is supposed to build competencies, novelty should be a foremost consideration and policies should be supportive of calculated risks in this regard. Therefore, our recommendation is that funding agencies should adopt a 'novelty first' policy and give directions to the peer review team to take special care in assessing novelty and feasibility of each proposal in the most judicious way. Apart from this, we only provide guideline on the sequence at which peer review should be conducted based on the output of the quantitative/scientometric framework. The procedure for the same is discussed next.

As there can be two scenarios possible for the process of shortlisting of proposals for each group (groups should be strictly based on age or effective career span of the applicants), these are discussed next.

Scenario-1: All the proposals of top $y N/M$ or $y N/M^*$ high scoring candidates are having tremendous merit and potential than the proposals of the rest in the group (i.e., the non-rejected ones among proposals from low CS scored candidates). Here, specially note that the merit of proposals based on the pre-decided qualitative parameters (both generic and subject specific) are evaluated here, not the applicants.

As proposals from the list of top y N/M or y N/M* CS valued proposals in this group are sound and meritorious, these can be shortlisted and others can be rejected (as in scenario 1 shown in fig. 3).

Scenario-2: One or more of the proposals of top y N/M or y N/M* high scoring candidates are not up to the mark and one or more of the proposals from the rest in the group (i.e., the non-rejected proposals from low CS scored candidates) appears to be equally or more meritorious than the debated ones from high scoring candidates. Here, specially note that the merit of proposals based on the pre-decided qualitative parameters (both generic and subject specific) are evaluated here, not the applicants.

As there is a difficulty to get (y N/M) or (y N/M*) eligible proposals for shortlisting (scenario 2 shown in fig. 3), then the proposals of the applicants in high scored CS list that are dubious to be placed in the vacant positions can be compared against fairly promising ones that are not removed from the list of low scoring applicants' proposals and final shortlisting can be made after this comparative review. If proposals by both top CS listed candidates and low CS listed candidates are not good enough according to the peer review parameters including novelty, then no proposal in the group shall be shortlisted for further consideration.

This can be repeated in all the M or M* groups.

Fig. 3 Peer review procedure in the proposed Informed peer review framework

Now, these shortlisted applications can go for high level committee and invited for presentation of the proposals eventually leading to the final selection of the proposals.

Since it is difficult to demonstrate the whole process with real-data, we are demonstrating the quantitative/scientometric framework i.e., the framework to be used by the first team with an example of one author profile.

Demonstration of the quantitative/scientometric framework

Consider the following sorting author profile shown in table 1, after all the processes from step 1, after obtaining keywords related each publication and creation of W-K network (step 1), and after creation of W-C^[R] network and through the first injection/matching process, the relevance-weighted W-K network or W-K^[R] network (step 2).

After second injection in step 3, the W-K^[R] network can be converted into W-K^{[R]*} network. Upon weighted indegree analysis of the second mode of the W-K^{[R]*} network, thematic strengths associated with each thematic area associated with the author can be obtained. Top 15 of such thematic areas is shown in table 2 to demonstrate computation of relevance-incorporated expertise indices.

From table 2, the $x^{[R]}$ and $x(g)^{[R]}$ indices of the sample author are found to be 6 and 8. This indicates that the author is supposed to have six core competency areas and 2 potential core competency areas. These areas are also given in the table. This information cannot be obtained by h and g indices. In this fashion, expertise areas (core competency and potential core competency areas) of all the applicants can be computed and this along with the information of strength in these areas and other information that are required by the decision framework, CS values can be computed for all the applicants from the computed values of α, β, γ and δ .

Table 1. Sorted sample author profile ($h=6$ and $g=9$)

Rank	Citation s	Citations/Ran k	Rank squared	Cumulative citations	Cumulative citations/Rank squared
1	27	27	1	27	27
2	18	9	4	45	11.25
3	9	3	9	54	6
4	8	2	16	62	3.875
5	8	1.6	25	70	2.8
6	7	1.166667	36	77	2.138889
7	5	0.714286	49	82	1.673469
8	5	0.625	64	87	1.359375
9	3	0.333333	81	90	1.111111
10	3	0.3	100	93	0.93
11	2	0.181818	121	95	0.785124
12	1	0.083333	144	96	0.666667
13	1	0.076923	169	97	0.573964
14	1	0.071429	196	98	0.5
15	0	0	225	98	0.435556
16	0	0	256	98	0.382813
17	0	0	289	98	0.3391
18	0	0	324	98	0.302469
19	0	0	361	98	0.271468
20	0	0	400	98	0.245
21	0	0	441	98	0.222222
22	0	0	484	98	0.202479

Illustration of the decision framework

After grouping candidates into effective age-based groups, informed peer review can be conducted with the help of CS values and final shortlisting can be done by carefully following the procedures. Since it is difficult to obtain real data for demonstration of the decision framework, we can only illustrate the framework in the following way. Suppose if A, B and C are three thematic areas considered for thrust-area based funding, and while grouping candidates into age-based groups suppose if there are 3 age-based groups ($M=3$) and in one of the age-based groups, if there are five candidates 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 with their core competency and potential core competency areas as given in table 3 and thematic strengths in those areas as given in table 4, computation of α , β , γ and δ can be found in tables 3 and 4, where maximum thematic strengths of candidates for the areas A, B and C in the whole set of candidates are 200, 100 and 50 respectively.

Table 2. Computation of relevance-incorporated expertise indices

Rank	Thematic areas	Thematic strength (relevance-incorporated)	Thematic strength/ Rank	Rank squared	Cumulative strength	Cumulative strength/ Rank squared
1	Engineering	11.407	11.407	1	11.407	11.407
2	Citation network analysis	11.258	5.629	4	22.665	5.6663
3	Mutual Contribution	9.378	3.126	9	32.043	3.5603
4	Interdisciplinarity	8.55	2.1375	16	40.593	2.5371
5	Nanotechnology	7.846	1.5692	25	48.439	1.9376
6	Biotechnology	6.921	1.1535	36	55.36	1.5378
7	Scientometrics	5.953	0.8504	49	61.313	1.2513
8	Path analysis	5.468	0.6835	64	66.781	1.0435
9	Search path count	5.24	0.5822	81	72.021	0.8891
10	Affiliation networks	4.824	0.4824	100	76.845	0.7685
11	Integrated approach	3.576	0.3251	121	80.421	0.6646
12	Information technology	3.375	0.2813	144	83.796	0.5819
13	Prediction	3.36	0.2585	169	87.156	0.5157
14	Energy Recommendation	2.502	0.1787	196	89.658	0.4574
15	system	0.705	0.047	225	90.363	0.4016

Table 3. Computation of α and β for five candidates in group 1

Candidate in Group 1	Core competency areas	Potential core competency areas	$T \cap T_x^{[R]}$	$T \cap (T_x(g)^{[R]}/T_x^{[R]})$	α	β
1	A, D, F, G, H	B, K, N	A	B	0.333	0.333
2	A, B, D, H, J	F, G, L, M	A, B		0.667	
3	B, C, D, J, K, L	A, F, H, M	B, C	A	0.667	0.333
4	A, B, C, D, H	E, F, G, M	A, B, C		1	
5	B, D, J, K, L, M, N	A, C, E, F, H	B	A, C	0.333	0.667

Table 4. Computation of γ and δ for five candidates in group 1

Candidate in Group 1	Thematic strength in A	Thematic strength in B	Thematic strength in C	γ	δ
1	50	40		0.143	0.114
2	80	50		0.371	0
3	60	70	50	0.343	0.171
4	200	90	30	0.914	0
5	60	90	30	0.257	0.257

Now the composite scores of candidates 1 to 5, according to eqn. (5) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CS of candidate 1} &= 0.35 \alpha + 0.15 \beta + 0.35 \gamma + 0.15 \delta \\ &= 0.35 \times 0.333 + 0.15 \times 0.333 + 0.35 \times 0.143 + 0.15 \times 0.114 \\ &= \mathbf{0.234} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, CS of other candidates are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CS of candidate 2} &= 0.35 \times 0.667 + 0.15 \times 0 + 0.35 \times 0.371 + 0.15 \times 0 \\ &= \mathbf{0.363} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CS of candidate 3} &= 0.35 \times 0.667 + 0.15 \times 0.333 + 0.35 \times 0.343 + 0.15 \times 0.171 \\ &= \mathbf{0.429} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CS of candidate 4} &= 0.35 \times 1 + 0.15 \times 0 + 0.35 \times 0.914 + 0.15 \times 0 \\ &= \mathbf{0.67} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CS of candidate 5} &= 0.35 \times 0.333 + 0.15 \times 0.667 + 0.35 \times 0.257 + 0.15 \times 0.257 \\ &= \mathbf{0.345} \end{aligned}$$

Now, if there are three vacancies, then $N=3$ and the committee decide to entertain a scale factor for shortlist of three (i.e., they are ready to spend time for interviewing 3 times the number of candidates from which actual selection will be done for N vacancies), then the number of possible shortlisted candidates from group 1 would be, $y^* (N/M)= 3*(3/3)= 3$.

So, in order to shortlist three candidates, the proposals are examined (peer reviewed) in the order of candidate 1, candidate 5, candidate 2, candidate 3 and candidate 4 (least scored ones to best scored one). Suppose if proposals by any or both of low scoring candidates such as 1 and 5 are found to be of great merit or potential, these will be kept on hold and rest will be rejected. This can be used to tackle two scenarios that can arise.

Scenario-1: All the proposals of top 3 high scoring candidates are having tremendous merit and potential.

Then, the proposals by candidates 1 and 5 will be rejected and candidates 4, 3 and 2 will be shortlisted from this group.

Scenario-2: One or some of the proposals of top 3 high scoring candidates are not up to the mark.

Then, the proposals by candidates 1 and 5 will be reconsidered and if one or both are found to be having better merit and potential than the proposals by toppers that are not found to be having good merit, proposals of candidates 1 and 5 can be considered for shortlisting.

However, the fact that their CS values were found to be comparatively less should be kept in note and if upon interview these proposals are finally selected for funding, if necessary proper training or handholding or guidance should be provided to these candidates to get them trained themselves for better execution of the tasks envisioned in the proposal to ensure that the projects bring fruitful outcomes.

Discussion

As discussed in the introduction, both pure peer review process and indicator-based assessment of research performance, especially for funding decisions (ex-ante) in thrust areas have their own limitations. Limited availability of experts for peer review in emerging thrust areas, tendency to select and apply parameters used in one discipline (possibly one of the parent disciplines) to an interdisciplinary field, less systematic procedures to reach at a consensus among the committee members, dominance or higher degree of influence of one or more active/influential members on the selection process that even overrule the intended purpose of committee (i.e., for ensuring the reduction of effect of judgemental biases) are some of the drawbacks of the peer review process (for example see Bendiscioli, 2019 and London, 2021 for more on limitations of peer review in science funding) Despite the fact that the rise of the field of bibliometrics/Scientometrics has allured and is still alluring funding decisionmakers with an alternative, its own set of drawbacks diminished the pace of its wide usage at least in the past two decades. Though Scientometricians contributed several indicators for performance assessment of actors of science and technology at different levels over the past six decades, except for a few, others are not that much known to be in use, mostly due to the difficulty in interpretation of these due to their sophistication. The indicators such as JIF, h -index, etc., are the mostly widely preferred as well as used (and misused) by the decisionmakers, mostly due to their simplicity in computation even though some of the drawbacks of these indicators were acknowledged by Garfield and Hirsch themselves at the time of their introduction. Two of the misuse of h -index (relatively newer among the two and more widely used) for ex-ante

assessment at individual level are rooted in its usage (i) to compare individuals who are at different stages of their careers and (ii) for decisions in a research context such as in thrust area funding applications though it is known to be an ‘overall’ productivity indicator. Even if there is an attempt for contextualization, still *h*-index faces drawbacks discussed by Lathabai et al. (2017) that hinders its usage in contextual productivity assessment and thereby in thrust area funding decisions. Another unhealthy practice is the tendency to develop ad hoc procedures for usage of indicators in ex-ante evaluations of research proposals (mostly without proper understanding on when and how to use these indicators) and the reuse of this procedure in future selection processes too.

Thus, informed peer review is viewed upon as an attempt to minimize the effect of limitations that are intrinsic in both peer review (qualitative) as well as indicator-based (quantitative) assessment. Major drawback of the informed peer review, revealed from related literature, that poses threat to its wider applicability is the time requirement. Another one is the lack of a systematic framework or procedure that is comprehensive as well as considers responsible use of indicators too to conduct the informed peer review process, especially in thrust area funding decisions. This work attempted to address gap by proposing a novel set of expertise indicators at the individual level, and also a comprehensive framework that outlines how to use the expertise indices to develop a composite score that can give an idea about the level of agreement of the thematic portfolio of an individual and themes that are considered in the call for funding and the soundness/proficiency of the individual.

The proposed framework addresses the task of determination of the suitability and soundness of an individual to be considered for the evaluation process through a novel set of expertise indices that retains the merits of *h*-index and its popular variant namely *g*-index but provides even more crucial information than these *h*-type indicators. This can be considered as an effective way of adaptive utilization of the simple but useful rationale behind the design of these *h*-type indicators while avoiding its misuse in contextual productivity assessment and thereby thrust area funding decisions. Further, the recommendation in the framework to classify the proposals according to the effective age of applicants, that ensure comparison and ranking among individuals that are almost in the same career phase eliminates any chances of the commonly found misuse of *h*-index or *h*-type indicators in ex-ante assessment, i.e., its usage in comparing individuals at different career phases. While this ensures the responsible use of indicators, the responsible use and reuse of framework for thrust area-based funding decisions is addressed by recommending the usage of two dedicated teams for the execution of informed peer review and proper demarcated work allocation in a sequential fashion between the teams. However, the provision to keep the thematic areas considered for the call unknown to first team and revelation of the thematic areas to the second team ‘just-in-time’ prior to the execution of decision framework might reduce the possibility of any voluntary or involuntary activities that might favour one or some of the candidates. At the same time, provision for second team to seek clarification or aid (especially in computation of CS values) from a learned representative of the first team leaves out the chances for misinterpretation of the results from Scientometric framework by second team. The possibility in ending up with funding low quality proposals from eminent individuals (which happens often in evaluation exercises that over rely on indicators) are also attempted to be checked in the framework by providing suitable guidelines to act in this scenario, i.e., scenario 2 in the peer review phase. Though the informed peer review framework may sound like a costly and time-consuming affair by the standards of usual informed peer review procedures, especially since there is an initial need to recruit trained scientometric experts or train newly recruited people with moderate scientometric expertise for building the first team, this can turn out to be otherwise due to its potential for long-term service. However, this speculation can be validated on post-implementation basis only. Barring this

minor drawback, which is inherent in any informed peer review exercises, the framework can do justice to most of the purposes for which it is conceived.

Conclusion

In this era of escalating concerns about the responsible use of indicators for quantitative assessment of research and the limitations of peer review, informed peer review is one of the relatively reliable options that can be incorporated in countries eyeing for formulation of performance-based funding decisions, especially when there is a need for thrust-area based funding at individual level. For addressing the prevailing gap due to the widely recognized limitations in the extensively used indicators like h -index and IF, a set of indicators namely relevance-incorporated expertise indicators, which is an improvement of the recently proposed expertise indicators such as x and $x(g)$ indices for institutional performance assessment that are inspired by h and g indices, are introduced and based on that an assessment framework for informed peer review is developed. The construct of the framework is in such a way that funding agencies need to constitute a team having bibliometric analytics expertise headed by a specialist scientometrician and support their data and analytical needs including access to databases for carrying out the quantitative/scientometric framework. A diligently designed procedure is (given in the methodology section) to be followed by this team and their results and inputs are to be transferred to the experts carrying out peer review (team 2) for executing the decision framework (which is also given in the methodology section) and they can seek the help of the leading scientometrician of the team 1 if any clarification is required. An example is provided for demonstrating the quantitative/scientometric framework, that clearly established the usability of the framework and why it can be preferred over h -index for thrust-area based funding decisions. The working of decision framework part is also explained using an illustrative example. The comprehensive framework for informed peer review devised in this work, if implemented is anticipated to bring long-term benefits in terms of cost and time for the evaluation processes and there is inherent flexibility in the design to incorporate timely modifications.

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